

Mechanism of Accountability and Auditing: Public Sector Scenarios of Bangladesh

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Abstract

The study examined the procedures and guidelines employed in the audit of public sector accounts in line with statutory and professional requirements. It also ascertained the extent to which accountability, effectiveness and efficiency of audit mechanism are being promoted in Bangladesh. Data were gathered through email survey to the staff of the Office of the Comptroller and Auditor General (OCAG), the Supreme Audit Institution of Bangladesh is responsible for auditing government receipts and public spending and to ascertain whether expenditures have yielded value for money in government offices, public bodies and statutory organizations, on the problems facing the audit and accountability system. Cross tabulations and Chi-square were used to analyze the data. The study revealed that the internal control systems in Bangladesh are very weak; audit procedures and accountability are as well ineffective due to political interference and lack of skills of some auditing staff. Based on the findings, an effective internal control system free from interference is needed. There is also the need for upgrading the skills of auditing personnel and also strict adherence to statutory and professional standards. Some of these changes require political will at Government level.

Keywords: Accountability; Public Sector; Bangladesh.

Introduction

Public sector audit has experienced considerable expansion throughout the world. The reason for this is concern for more accountable and transparent governance, which has resulted in a large increase in the number of accounts and sophistication of financial reporting. The expansion has

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brought with it an added demand for in terms of objectives, sources of revenue and basis of recording accounts, responsibility and accountability among others. It is useful however, to distinguish between audit and other forms of regulation and inspection. Public audit applies to almost every public sector body and is relatively wide-ranging, from certifying the accounts to examinations of economy, efficiency and effectiveness. The audit function and the form in which audit results are reported tend to reinforce the traditional line of sector accountability to elected representatives rather than establish new forms of accountability. In Bangladesh the appointment, the authority and the duties of the Auditor General are described in Constitution of the Peoples Republic of Bangladesh. Briefly, the Auditor General or any person authorized by him or her is to audit, without directions or control of any other authority, the accounts of all offices, the courts and all collection and administration of public monies and assets. The Auditor-General or any delegated person authorized by him is permitted to have access to the books, records and other documents relating the accounts. Because of rapidly changing technology and the increasing demand for good governance-transparency and accountability in the public sector it is important to revise auditing practices in respect of adequacy, reliability, efficiency and effectiveness in promoting these ends. Hence the objects of this study, using Bangladesh as a case study, are

- To ascertain whether the method, procedures and guidelines employed in the audit of public sector accounts are in accordance with statutory, professional and ethical standards.
- To ascertain the effectiveness and efficiency of audit mechanism and accountability as practiced by the public sector and to recommend ways of improving existing methods of auditing public accounts.

Office of the Comptroller and Auditor General

Performance Audit has been incorporated in the audit portfolio of the Office of the Comptroller & Auditor General of Bangladesh [OCAG] since 1999. The OCAG realizes that in Bangladesh, where resource constraint is a major issue and a significant amount of public expenditure

is financed by public debt, an independent evaluation of the economy, efficiency and effectiveness with which public resources have been used is essential. Therefore, Performance Audit was introduced by OCAG in addition to Financial and Compliance Audits for ensuring accountability of the executive to the Parliament and ultimately to the taxpayers for optimal utilization of public resources.

The Constitution of the Peoples' Republic of Bangladesh provides OCAG with the mandate to perform Performance Audits. The mandate of the CAG, to carry out all audits, is derived from Article 128 of the Constitution which provides the CAG with discretionary power in deciding how, what and when to audit. Moreover, the Public Accounts Committee [PAC] of the 5th Parliament expressed its concern in 1998 for greater accountability and requested the Auditor General to conduct Performance Audits alongside annual financial and compliance audits.

Performance Audit Activities in OCAG

Performance Audit was first piloted by OCAG in 1999 in response to the demand of the PAC. A Performance Audit Cell was created and four Pilot Audits were carried out by the Cell with officials who had undergone extensive trainings in the relevant fields. The reports were finalized in January 2002 and were submitted to Parliament. The reports are:

- Performance Audit on Printing, Publication and Distribution of Text Books
- Performance Audit on the Power Distribution System of Dhaka Electricity Supply Authority [DESA]
- Performance Audit of the Industrial Parks of Bangladesh Small and Cottage Industries Corporation [BSCIC]
- Performance Audit on the Health Care Services of the Chittagong Medical College Hospital

After the successful piloting of Performance Audit in Bangladesh, OCAG conducted performance audits regularly through the nine Audit Directorates.

Then in 2005 a Performance Audit Directorate was established to coordinate performance audit activities of OCAG. The organogram of the Performance Audit Directorate is given below:

The main responsibility assigned to the Performance Audit Directorate is the enhancement of performance audit capability of OCAG by:

- Providing advice to other Audit Directorates
- Supervising performance audit works of other Audit Directorate
- Conducting performance audits
- Working as research wing of OCAG for improving audit methodology
- Developing training modules and deliver trainings
- Developing Quality Checklists
- Setting up a Resource Centre

Context of Accountability and Internal Audit in Bangladesh

Accountability and audit are two correlated concepts. In accounting discipline, sometimes it is stated that audit starts when preparation of accounts are complete. A budget recipient of the public fund is accountable for spending this taxpayer's money. Parliament as principal allocates this money to the line ministries who collectively form the

budget recipient sector. They are authorized to spend the money, manage properly the spending of this money and finally are responsible to show a true and fair view of their activities presenting the accounts at the end of the financial year.

Auditable firm keeps the ministries accountable via secretaries conducting different types of audit. There are other organs and techniques to evaluate, monitor and assess ministries' job but audit bears the prime responsibility in the function of keeping the accountable in using the public fund. So, accountability depends on audit activities. And there exists a relationship between the effectiveness of audit with auditor's credibility and simultaneously of client's role.

This section covers important issues related to the status of accountability and audit in Bangladesh. Audit the mostly recognized tool to ensure accountability is exercised by the SAI of Bangladesh. Role of audit in ensuring accountability, role of Office of the Comptroller and Auditor General of Bangladesh in this regard is described here.

Role of Audit in ensuring Accountability:

Audit is often called the '*eyes and ears*' in monitoring the volume, type and nature of public fund. It is vital that the internal audit functions properly that is done by internal control mechanism of any entity, the external audit provides aids to management. If there is no audit, it might happen that huge anomalies are being carried on in the client's end. Several audit reports can be cited where even unspent balance is one of the large volume that were kept unutilized and from this instance of mismanagement serious financial irregularities could have been not examined and resolved unless there would exist audit.

The Office of the Comptroller and Auditor General (OCAG), the Supreme Audit Institution (SAI) of Bangladesh is responsible for auditing government receipts and public spending and to ascertain whether expenditures have yielded Value For Money (VFM) in government offices, public bodies and statutory organizations. Appointed by the President of the republic, the Comptroller and Auditor General (CAG)

heads the Supreme Audit Institution. CAG has the mandate to determine the scope and extent of audit.

The Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh provides the CAG with complete independence i.e. he or she is not subject to any other authority having access to all documents required for conducting audit. Director General, the head of the audit directorate is responsible for conducting audit on behalf of the CAG in the government offices as well as the public sector undertakings. Audit observations involving serious financial irregularities are initially developed into Advance Paras (AP) and subsequently Draft Paras (DP) after taking into consideration the replies received from the concerned auditee organization and the Principal Accounting Officer (PAO)- Secretary of the Ministry/Division. The DPs are incorporated in the audit report after approval of the CAG. Alongside traditional approach to carry out financial, compliance or regularity audits, the office is now conducting performance audit to determine economy, efficiency and effectiveness in the management of public resources, thereby adding value to the governance issues.

In recent years there is an increased use of Information Technology (IT) in the government offices; as a result scope for the IT audit has also increased manifold. To keep pace with the client firm OCAG has created a core IT Audit group and moving forward to creating an IT Audit cell in the OCAG to foster the IT auditing activities.

To ensure this, OCAG works in different ways- through the application of standards set by OCAG, International bodies like International Organization of Supreme Audit Institutions (INTOSAI), Asian Organization of Supreme Audit Institutions (ASOSAI) and other standard setting organizations like ICMAB (The Institute of Cost and Management Accountants of Bangladesh) and other legal bodies. OCAG activities include-

1. Continuous development of own standards and adoption of relevant standards set by other institutions;
2. Innovations in operational areas while conducting audit;
3. Monitoring, supervision and follow-up of the audit observations;
4. Reporting to Parliament through regular and special audits;

5. Communication with Public Accounts Committee;
6. Continuous communication with auditee entities and other stakeholders.

Conceptual Framework for Auditing Public Sector Accounts

Auditing of Public Accounts - The position of An Auditor General was first created in England in June 1866 with enactment of Audit Act of 1866. In Bangladesh, there are three areas of public sector auditing, namely:

- Accountancy audit
- Appropriation audit
- Administrative audit

Accountancy Audit - Deals with the rules or the principles of accounts by examining whether the accounts have been prepared in accordance with accounting concepts and postulations and that all expenditure payment vouchers, receipts, and the like are treated accordingly.

Appropriation Audit - Involves a thorough securitization of estimates or budget in comparison with the yearly accounts prepared by the accounting officers of each agency of government

Administrative Audit - Involves close monitoring whether the agency of government is being run accordingly to the rules and regulations.

Concept of Public Accountability and Audit Accountability - There is not generally accepted definition of the term accountability. Adesola (2001), maintains that accountability is one of these terms employed in government studies, which suffers from frequent misuse and imprecise or varying meaning, Adesola however goes on to define it as duty imposed on any person who holds power or authority or is in position of trust to act and on behalf of another person to take responsibility for his action and to render account of stewardship whenever it is necessary to do so. Anonymous (2002), author also considers accountability not to be a simple notion which is often not well understood and its effective application to the complexities of government today can be quite daunting.

Johnson (1974) argued that the definitional problem may be due in part to the fact that the traditional way of thinking about accountability in public administration represented an insufficient framework for analysis. Other

writers such as Day and Klein (1987) viewed accountability directed at community at large, rather than at the lines of constitutional accountability. In similar vein an Anonymous (2002) writer concedes that modern governance and management reflect contemporary pressures from various sources in society. These pressures involve:

- The emergence of essentially non-hierarchical relationships in many alternative
- Delivery approaches being tried today, such as network, partnerships and arrangements between the federal and state governments, where responsibilities may not be conferred from a senior to a one but agreement nonetheless assume accounting for results;
- The call for an increased focus on results and performance-based management by the public sector in addition to addressing concerns with the integrity of governance;
- The parallel call for providing greater flexibility and autonomy to government organizations and managers in order to achieve better results and
- The importance of transparency as an essential feature of public sector accountability.

These pressures determine which perspective of accountability is adopted. Consequently, accountability can be viewed from a number of perspectives. These are discussed below.

Perspective of Accountability

The Traditional Perspective - This is the simplest model, with a coherent chain-from official to official in the bureaucracy, from official to minister, from minister to parliament to the people. Under the traditional perspective, each official is technically accountable, through the hierarchical structure of the bureaucracy, to elected politicians and to the citizens. In the ideal traditional view, as under all other perspectives, honesty, integrity, impartiality and objectivity form the code of behavior of officers as they administer rules decided by the politicians.

The Democratic Perspective - Participatory forms of democracy as channels for holding public administration to account. These channels may

have been downgraded in favor of others by recent reform initiatives; they do however, still exist and have the potential to impact on the activities of public administration.

The Professional Perspective - This is based on what Clarke (1994) described as the view sold to the public that in the 1960s and 1970s that both bureaucracy and professionalism represented transcendent sets of rules and knowledge which guaranteed the neutrality of state intervention. However, in the 1980s and 1990s bureaucracy and professionalism have been identified as partisan interests who require the creation of new political disciplines to check their powers.

The Manager Perspective - Recognizes that accountability operates at two levels – the strategic level for which politicians are responsible and the operational level, which is the sphere of managers. The test of legitimacy of public service is the acceptability of the services it produces for the citizen. The shift in modern governments to setting clear objectives, measuring performance and separating police from administration makes officials as much accountable for the end product as politicians. However, Stewart and Stocker (1995), argue that this shift is the ideal, which may not always be achieved in practice.

The Governance Perspective - According to Rhodes (1996) it is difficult to define governance perspective because the term governance has acquired a multitude of different meanings. The governance perspective is, however, closely related to the managerialist frame of reference but moves beyond traditional institutions of governance by emphasizing the external dependence and fragmentation of the state, which inhibit its capacity to effectively govern.

According to Rhodes (2000), this perspective is more contemporary in recognizing the reality of partnerships and networks of arrangement in today's joined up public sector. According to Pierre and Stoker (2000), the governance perspective thus highlights the apparent tension between new forms of political coordination and steering on the one hand and a powerful legacy of channels and instruments for political accountability on the other.

The Regulatory Perspective - Emphasizes the use of authority, rules and standard setting, particularly displacing an earlier emphasis on public subsidies and directly provided services. Consequently is no longer ensured though line management relations with in clear hierarchical structures but through increased surveillance and audit and hands off regulation (Hood, 1999).

The Rational Choice Perspective - Is based on rational choice theory, which explains social phenomena from the beliefs and goals of individuals. According to this perspective only by focusing on individual political strategies of these actors could a true picture of accountability emerge? Dowding (2000) have however argued that rational choice perspective is not a rival to other perspectives in politics. Rather it is a method of studies, which illuminates other approaches and provide a dynamic explanation of their descriptive and categorical forms. This is more so if it is recognized that accountability goes beyond rendering stewardship. This is so because governing is a very complex process in which assessments are made whether ones use of allocation of resources is better or yields more benefits than another. This complexity has very serious consequence when decisions taken by public officers are brought under open and public scrutiny particularly by those who were either not parties to those decisions or are even incapable of appreciating the intricacies of such decisions.

Principles of Effective Accountability - The preceding sections discussed the various perspectives of looking at accountability. However, Anonymous (1997 and 2001) contend that there are five principles of effective accountability with each principle referring to an aspect of accountability especially to the newer forms of accountability relationships, such as through alternative service delivery mechanisms. The five principles are as follows:

- **Clear roles and responsibilities:** The roles and responsibilities of the parties in the accountability relationship should be well understood and agreed upon. Such an understanding provides the context within which both parties will respond and perform. Without this understanding and the required clarification, the basic underpinnings of an effective relationship would be absent.

- **Clear performance expectations:** The objectives being pursued, the accomplishments expected, this is, what each party is expected to contribute to the result, including the inputs and outputs to achieve the desired outcomes and the constraints to be expected should be explicit, understood and agreed upon. Without a clearly spelt out expected outcomes, it would be impossible to determine whether these outcomes have been realized.
- **Balanced expectations and capacities:** The performance expectations need to be clearly linked to and in balance with the capacity, that is, authorities, skills and resources of each party to deliver. The absence of a plausible link between what is expected and the authorities and resources supplied will tend to undermine the effectiveness of accountability. Consequently, expectations that are well beyond what is reasonable for the resources provided will not be believed. Accordingly effective accountability is enhanced by clarity of the links and balance, between resources and expected results.
- **Credible reporting:** Effective accountability requires reporting what has been accomplished to bodies to whom the parties are responsible (such as parliament) and to the other parties in the accountability relationship. For the report to be useful, it must be seen as credible and must be timely. It must describe results accomplished, resources and actions taken in light of the agreed expectations. The report must also attribute responsibility in some manner for shortcomings. Depending on the circumstances, reporting can be ongoing, periodic or both. In some situations, external audit can be used to enhance the credibility of performance information.
- **Reasonable review and adjustment:** A credible review and feedback on the performance achieved should be carried out by the accountable parties. Where achievements are below agreed levels, the causes of the under performance are recognized and necessary corrective actions are taken and possible adjustments to the accountability arrangement made and lessons-learned noted. An accountability relationship without follow-ups is clearly incomplete and unlikely to be effective.

Research Method

This study analyzes the effectiveness of OCAG ensuring accountability of the client firm of the OCAG. Thus it wants to find out what is the state of effectiveness of OCAG in ensuring accountability?

As previously stated the objective of this study is to examine the mechanism of audit and accountability in the public sector using Bangladesh as a case study. Primary data were mainly used and were obtained through a questionnaire survey. It was administered to 45 members of staff of the three audit departments in the headquarter office of the Auditor General and 40 responses were retrieved giving a response rate of 90%.

The questionnaire is thematic in nature with three sections. Section-A consists of five questions, which focuses on the internal control in operation in Bangladesh audit system. Section-B consists of eleven questions which relate to the system of auditing, while section-C consists of five questions, which relate to accountability in the public sector. On the whole, the questions discussed the systems of auditing and accountability in the public sector. The data collected were analyzed, using cross tabulations and the Pearson Chi-square test.

Results and Discussion

Internal Control Systems - Credibility of an audit depends, among other things, on internal controls. However, the survey results on effectiveness of internal controls, reported in Table 1, show that 70% of staff in the Auditor General's office do not perform any test on the internal control systems when auditing public sector accounts. Only about one quarter (26%) of the Auditor General's office reported that they perform such test control. A small number (4%) perform internal control tests occasionally. The main conclusion from Table 1 is that internal system control tests are generally not performed when auditing public sector accounts in Bangladesh.

Effectiveness of Internal Control System - Information in Table 2 shows that many of the staff of the Auditor General's Department who interviewed did not think the internal control systems were effective. Approximately one-third of the interviewees believed the internal control systems were effective compared with 38% who did not consider the

internal control systems were effective and 27% could not tell whether the control systems were effective. This finding may explain why 70% of interviewees did not perform these control checks.

Table 3 presents information on the mode of confirming the values of stores and stocks in the public sector during the course of an audit. According to this information, just over 50% the respondents acknowledged that stores and stock are physically counted during auditing compared to 22% who contended that stores and stocks are confirmed by observation. Sixteen percent of the respondents were of the opinion that stores and stocks are confirmed by studying the storekeeper's book only. The remaining 6% contend that stores and stocks are confirmed by all the three methods stated earlier.

The method of confirming the accuracy of entries is even worse where auditing of salaries and wages is concerned. As shown in Table 4, only 38% of the respondents were of the opinion that salaries and wages were audited against comprehensive staff lists. Thirty one percent of respondents believed that auditing of salaries and wages was done using performance evaluation card compared with 25% who believed it was done by checking the personal emolument cards. Only 5% of respondents believed that all the above-mentioned methods were used.

Table 5 reports the opinion of respondents regarding whether the auditing process conforms to statutory, professional and ethical standards. While 52% thought the auditing and accountability procedure in the state public sector was in accordance with statutory professional and ethical standard 48% believed that this was not the case. The large number of respondents believing that the system of audit and accountability in the state is not in accordance with statutory professional and ethical standard if true should be a worry.

Table 7 presents information on the perception of respondents on the extent to which accountability enhances efficiency in government operations. According to information in the table 7, 63% of respondents either agreed strongly or agreed that accountability enhances good governance. The remaining 37% disagreed that accountability has any impact on the efficiency of government operations.

Table 8 also paint the not-flattering opinion of the respondents about auditing and accountability process, with 38% of respondents contending that auditing enhances effective accountability while 43% held the opposite view. The remaining 19% of respondents could not say whether auditing and accountability of the public sector has any effect on effective accountability.

Testing of Hypothesis

Here, we use Chi-square statistics to test two hypotheses using our survey results. The hypotheses are to establish whether based on the survey results we can conclude that:

- Internal control systems in operation in the public sector accounts are effective,
- Whether auditing of public sector accounts in Bangladesh enhance accountability.

Hypothesis one

H_0 : The internal control system in operation in the public sector is not effective.

H_1 : The internal control in operation in the public sector account is effective.

The Chi-square is calculated from information in Table 9:

Computed Chi-square	3.448
Chi-square tabulated (5% level of significance)	9.49

Since the calculated Chi-square is less than Table value of Chi-square the null hypothesis that internal control systems in public sector are not effective is accepted.

Hypothesis Two

H_0 : Auditing of public sector account in the country does not enhance effective accountability.

H_1 : Auditing of public sector account in the country enhance effective accountability.

The Chi-square for testing hypothesis 2 is based on information in Table 10:

Computed Chi-square	3.9728
Chi-square tabulated (5% level of significance)	9.49

Since the calculated Chi-square is less than Table value of Chi-square the null hypothesis that auditing of public sector accounts in the country does not enhance effective accountability is accepted.

Concluding Comments

The guarantee of complete independence and non-interference in the work of audit department is essential for a quality audit work to be performed as well as effective line accountability. According to our results the internal control system is not considered to be effective by a sample of the staff of the Auditor General’s Department.

Furthermore, the system of auditing public sector accounts does not seem to enhance effective accountability. This may be attributed to the political interference experienced and non-independence of internal audit personnel and this prevents them doing their work as required by the Constitution.

Another important reason why the audit system is ineffective is that staff of the government audit department informs the Ministries and other public sector institutions of their visit ahead of time, which give sufficient time for covering up of any irregularity that the auditor may otherwise have noticed in the course of the audit work.

Some of these problems can be easily remedied while others are more intractable. For example, the staff of the Auditor General’s Department could be given adequate training over time.

Table 1: Use of internal control systems

Response	No. of respondents	
	No.	%
Often	21	26
Sometimes	3	4
Not at all	57	70
Total	81	100

Table 2: Effectiveness of internal control system

Response	No. of respondents	
	No.	%
Very effective	23	35
Not effective	36	38
Cannot assess	22	27
Total	81	100

Table 3: Mode of auditing stores and stocks

Response	No. of respondents	
	No.	%
Physical counting	45	56
Observation	18	22
Examining the storekeepers books	13	16
All the above	5	6
Total	81	100

Table 4: Mode of auditing salaries and wages

Response	No. of respondents	
	No.	%
Obtain comprehensive staff list	31	38
Obtain Performance evolution card of each staff	25	31
Cheek personal emolument card	20	25
All the above	5	6
Total	81	100

Table 5: Adherence to statutory, professional and ethical standards

Response	No. of respondents	
	No.	%
Yes	42	52
No	39	48
Total	81	100

Table 6: Adequacy of audit and accountability

Response	No. of respondents	
	No.	%
Yes	45	56
No	36	44
Total	81	100

Table 7: Effect of accountability on efficiency in government operations

Response	No. of respondents	
	No.	%
Strongly agree	28	35
Agree	23	28
Disagree	30	37
Total	81	100

Table 8: Effect of auditing of public sectors on efficiency accountability

Response	No. of respondents	
	No.	%
Very effective	31	38
Not effective	35	43
Can not assess	15	19
Total	81	100

Table 9: Opinion on effectiveness internal control system by departmental.
Expected and actual frequencies

Variables	Responses			
	Dept 1	Dept 2	Dept 3	Total
Very effective	11(10.790)	6(3.691) 6(8.519)	23	
Not effective	16(16.889)	4(5.778) 16(13.333)	36	
Can not assess	11(10.321)	3(3.531) 8(8.148)	22	
Total	38	13	30	81

Note: The expected frequencies are in parenthesis.

Table 10: Opinion on effectiveness of auditing public sectors to enhance effective accountability, expected frequencies and actual frequencies

Variables	Responses			
	Dept 1	Dept 2	Dept 3	Total
Yes	12(14.543)	6(4.975)	13(11.482)	31
No	19(16.420)	3(5.617)	13(12.963)	35
Can not assess	7(7.037)	4(2.407)	4(5.556)	15
Total	38	13	30	81

Note: The expected frequencies are in parenthesis,
Source: Computed by the author from survey result.

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